

Original Article

ICT COMPETENCY NEEDS OF BUSINESS EDUCATORS FOR EFFECTIVE PERFORMANCE IN COLLEGES OF EDUCATION IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study determined the ICT competency needs of business educators for effective performance in colleges of education in Anambra State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used in the study. The population for the study consists of 156 Business Educators in three colleges of education offering business education programmes in the state. The entire population was studied without sampling because the size was manageable. The instrument used for data collection was a four-point rating scale questionnaire containing 45 items in two sections according to the research questions. The instrument was validated by the three experts, two of them from Business and Entrepreneurship Education Department and one in Measurement and Evaluation option from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education, both from the Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. The study was carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria, using a descriptive survey research design. Cronbach's Alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient, which yielded 0.89. Out of 156 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 149 copies were retrieved and used for analysis, representing a 95.51% return rate. Mean score ratings were used to answer the research questions, and t-test was used to test the two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at 147 degree of freedom. Findings of the study revealed that networking and computer operation competencies are highly needed by the business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State for effective performance. Based on the findings, the study concludes that the identified ICT competencies are needed by business educators for effective performance. It was recommended among others that business educators in colleges of education in the area should develop networking and computer operation competencies for effective performance. While the government and concerned bodies should support and sponsor the business educators to in-service training on the acquisition of the identified ICT competency needs for effective job performance.

Keywords: ICT, competency needs, business educators, effective performance, networking competency, computer operation competency

INTRODUCTION

Business Education is an academic programme that involves the acquisition of skills, values, beliefs, and habits necessary for effective participation in commercial, industrial, and professional activities. It is an integral part of vocational education aimed at equipping students with relevant skills that make them functional in society as both producers and consumers of goods and services (Eze, 2016). For this reason, the various components of Business Education must be taught by well-trained professionals to ensure that learners acquire the competencies needed for meaningful engagement in the business world. With the introduction of technological innovations such as Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Business Education has been positively transformed. ICT enhances teaching and learning, promotes the development of digital skills, and equips students with business and management-related competencies required for effective job performance in today's digital economy.

Business Education is also one of the major occupational areas provided within vocational and technical education in Nigeria. It offers instruction in key areas such as accounting, marketing, and office technology and management (OTM). Major topics include office practice, bookkeeping, business mathematics, business communication, secretarial duties, word processing, and advertising (Ajisafe, Balarinwa & Ede, 2015). According to Edokpolor and Egbri (2017), the goals of Business Education include preparing students for specific office careers, equipping them with entrepreneurial and job-creation skills, and exposing them to comprehensive business knowledge supported by ICT. The first two goals reflect education for business, providing the knowledge, skills, competencies, and attitudes needed for gainful employment, while the third represents education about business, which lays a foundation for further studies at the graduate and postgraduate levels. As Ezeabii (2017) notes,

Business Education equips individuals with both practical and theoretical competencies required for performance in the business world, whether as paid employees or self-employed entrepreneurs.

Business Education at the tertiary level gained national prominence in Nigeria following the 1977 National Policy on Education, which recognized its role in equipping learners with employability skills for job creation, job retention, and career advancement (Okafor, 2017). At the tertiary level—specifically in universities and Colleges of Education—the programme prepares students for entry-level positions and provides the foundational knowledge required for post-secondary occupational training. According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013), tertiary education aims to develop proper societal values, enhance intellectual capacities, promote self-reliance, and produce useful members of society. Colleges of Education, which award the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), the minimum qualification for teaching in Nigeria, offer Business Education programmes in areas such as Office Technology and Management, Accounting, and Marketing Education. The National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) minimum standards (FRN, 2020) outline the objectives of Business Education at this level to include producing competent NCE graduates who can teach business subjects, promote vocational development, pursue further studies in Business Education, and acquire skills for office work and self-employment. The realization of these objectives, however, depends on the availability of well-equipped and professionally trained business educators capable of meeting the contemporary needs of students and the society.

In Colleges of Education, there are male and female business educators who are trained to implement the curriculum contents. Okeke (2017), points that business education programmes are not gender sensitive as male and female students and lecturers are found in the programme. The Business Educators are graduates or individuals who

completed the business education programme from accredited universities and colleges of education.

Business Educators are those people who have passed through and completed the programme in approved universities or colleges of education and are certified as qualified graduates who can be able to pass or transfer the requisite knowledge, values, and skills to students in the department of Business Education. Business Educators are those who train their students to solve business problems, plan for future growth, and strategize on how to run a business effectively through the teaching of different courses like accounting, human resource management, labour relations, finance, marketing, advertising, and office management. Business educators are expected to possess certain level of competencies in different fields, including ICT, to deliver their instructional content effectively.

Competency is the ability to adequately and successfully combine and perform necessary actions in any context to achieve specific tasks or objectives. According to Bakare, Okereke, and Obe (2017), competency is the combination of knowledge, skills, and attitudes required for carrying out a task. Competence serves as a motivated pattern of knowledge, skills, and interpersonal abilities deployed to undertake a valued job. It is the combination of observable and measurable knowledge, skills, and abilities, as well as personal attributes that contribute to enhanced employee performance, which ultimately result in organizational success (Ismail & Mohammed, 2015). The competency needs of business educators in the modern age are digitally based on ICTs and their application in business education programme. There is a need for Business Educators to possess these ICT competencies and their application in this era of globalization to be able to meet global competitiveness.

Information and Communication Technology is an integrated technology for gathering, processing, delivering, and storing information. Nwachukwu

(2017) and Digital Literacy (2017), point out that ICT involves all the technologies employed in order to facilitate the collection, storage, retrieval, and communication by the fastest means. The advent of computers in the 19th century ushered in the internet, digital telephone systems, projectors, electronic commerce (e-commerce), electronic banking (e-banking), electronic learning (e-learning), teleconferencing, and many others. According to Olaniyi (2022), organizations expect their staff to be ICT literate so they can access information promptly, thereby reducing costs and enhancing productivity. According to Ajagbelen (2016), ICTs are powerful enabling tools for educational change and reform when used appropriately. Different ICTs help expand access to education, stress the relevance of education to the workplace, and raise educational quality by creating an active process connected to life. ICT has made an impact on the quality and quantity of teaching, learning, and research in conventional and or distance education institutions that utilize it. For employees such as business educators to effectively use ICT to deliver their instructional contents they need basic competencies which, according to Okeke (2015), include computer networking competency, computer operation competency, hardware maintenance competency, software competency, and programming competency, among others. ICT networking competency is the knowledge and skills of linking one computer to the other. Computer networking according to Ajagbelen (2016), could be local area network and wide area network. With the networking competency business educators can link a computer device to another or use internet connectivity in operating a computer.

Computer operation competency is concerned with the ability of an individual to use knowledge, skills and attitude in operating a computer system to effective performance of a job. Odokor (2017), points that computer operation skills are the dexterity needed for one to effectively utilize a

computer system to perform a task creditably. Computer operation competency may not be carried out successfully without hardware maintenance competency.

In Anambra State, there is need for the colleges of education business educators to possess ICT facilities utilization competencies as the digitalization of different sectors has increased. Anambra State is one of the states in South-East geo-political Zone of Nigerian. The State name was formed in 1976 from the former east central state, the state is named after Omambala River, a River that runs through the State. With the increasing level of commercial activities in Anambra State with digital technology, there is need to train the students of business education with business educators that are ICT competent. Odokor (2017) noted that there is lack of ICT competency amongst the business educators. This necessitated the investigation into the ICT competency needs of the business educators. It is against this background that the study investigated ICT competency needs of Business Educators in colleges of education for effective performance in Anambra State.

Problem of the Study

In today's digital and globalized economy, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has become an essential tool for enhancing teaching, learning, and professional practice. ICT offers limitless possibilities, enabling educators to access and share information efficiently, collaborate across distances, solve problems creatively, and teach with greater effectiveness. In Business Education, ICT supports curriculum delivery by helping lecturers demonstrate concepts, engage learners, analyse business data, and equip students with the digital competencies required for the 21st century workplace.

However, despite the central role of ICT in modern education, teaching in Business Education programmes within Nigerian tertiary institutions, particularly Colleges of Education in Anambra State

appears to be lagging behind global expectations. Observation indicates that many graduates of Colleges of Education do not possess adequate digital competencies for effective job performance in today's technologically driven business environment. This suggests that some Business Educators themselves may not be fully ICT-compliant or may not be effectively utilizing available ICT facilities in teaching and learning. As Olaniyi (2022) observed, graduates of Business Education in Nigeria have not attained appreciable proficiency in using ICT to solve accounting and other business related problems in line with 21st century global standards.

This situation has contributed to the production of students with insufficient digital skills, leading to poor job readiness, vulnerability to manipulations, and increasing unemployment. The gap between the possibilities offered by ICT and the current instructional practices in Business Education calls for urgent attention. Therefore, the problem of this study is: What are the ICT competency needs of Business Educators for effective performance in Colleges of Education in Anambra State?

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the ICT competency needs of business educators for effective performance in colleges of education in Anambra State. Specifically, the study determined the:

1. Networking competencies needed by business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State for effective performance.
2. Computer operating competency needed by business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State for effective performance.

Research Questions

This study was guided by two research questions. They are as follows;

1. What are the networking competency needs of business educators in colleges of education for effective performance?

2. What are the computer operating competency needs of business educators in colleges of education for effective performance?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

H0₁. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State on networking competencies they need for effective performance.

H0₂ Significant difference does not exist between the mean scores of male and female business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State on the computer operation competencies they need for effective performance.

Method

The study was carried out in Anambra State, Nigeria, using a descriptive survey research design. Anambra state has a population of over six million people, with most residents engaged in farming, fishing, trading, and various forms of industry and craftsmanship. It is also known for its strong commercial centers, vibrant markets, and growing small-scale manufacturing activities. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided

Results

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of the Business Educators in Colleges of Education in Anambra State on Networking Competencies They Need for Effective Performance

S/N	Ability to:	Male n= 57		Female n= 92		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
1	identify necessary components for computers to network	3.14	0.77	3.15	0.78	3.15	0.77	A
2	follow detailed instructions for configuring networks clients	3.32	0.54	3.29	0.55	3.30	0.54	A
3	allocate required software while connecting to the server	3.04	0.79	3.01	0.83	3.01	0.81	A
4	follow instruction while managing the structure of an internet	3.19	0.66	3.18	0.69	3.19	0.68	A
5	install basic configuration options for equipment such as router and switches	3.16	0.73	3.14	0.74	3.15	0.73	A
6	locate resources to explore network communication topics	2.95	0.87	2.91	0.89	2.93	0.88	A
7	maintain web servers	3.04	0.78	3.05	0.76	3.05	0.76	A
8	use common networking technologies	2.93	0.80	2.92	0.77	2.93	0.78	A
9	perform basic operation task	3.11	0.79	3.09	0.77	3.09	0.77	A
10	create users' relationships	3.42	0.57	3.43	0.56	3.43	0.56	A
11	use offline reference materials as additional resources to connect to a network	3.18	0.73	3.21	0.75	3.19	0.74	A

the study. The population for the study consists of 156 Business Educators in three colleges of Education offering business education programmes in Anambra State. The entire population was studied without sampling because the size was manageable. The instrument used for data collection was a four-point rating scale questionnaire developed by the researcher, containing 30 items in two sections in line with the research questions, with strongly agree (SA), agree (A), disagree (D), and strongly disagree (SD) as response options. The instrument was validated by the three experts, two of them from the Business and Entrepreneurship Education Department and one in the Measurement and Evaluation option from the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education both from Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient which yielded 0.89. Out of 156 copies of the questionnaire distributed 149 copies were properly filled and used for data analysis representing 95.51% return rate. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test was used to test the two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at 147 degree of freedom.

12	use electronic mails	3.37	0.56	3.38	0.57	3.38	0.56	A
13	Upload a text file and send it as electronic mails	3.14	0.83	3.14	0.83	3.14	0.83	A
Cluster Mean/SD		3.15	0.72	3.14	0.73	3.15	0.72	A

Table 1 shows that overall mean score ranging from 2.93 to 3.43 showing agree. This means that the respondents view the items as the networking competency needs of business educators in colleges of education for effective performance in Anambra State. The overall cluster mean of 3.15

further indicates that the items are the networking competency needs of business educators in colleges of education for effective performance in Anambra State. The low standard deviation of 0.72 indicates that the respondents have similar opinion to the items.

Hypothesis 1

Table 2: Summary of t-test analysis of difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State on networking competencies they need for effective performance

Variables	N	T	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	57	.030	147	.976	.02346	.78981	NS
Female	92						

Table 2 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significant and 147 degree of freedom for the 13 items is 0.030 with a significant value of 0.976. Since the significant value of 0.976 is more than the 0.05 level of significant the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant

difference regarding the items on the mean ratings of male and female business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State with Respect to networking competency needs for effective performance.

Table 3: Mean ratings and standard deviation of the business educators on the computer operating competency needs of business educators in colleges of education for effective performance in Anambra State

S/N	Ability to:	Male n= 57		Female n= 92		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
14	start(boot) and shutdown a computer system	3.05	0.81	3.07	0.85	3.06	0.83	A
15	use icons options	3.30	0.65	3.30	0.68	3.30	0.66	A
16	access an application	3.37	0.67	3.34	0.68	3.35	0.68	A
17	create a document	3.33	0.66	3.30	0.66	3.32	0.66	A
18	print a document	3.39	0.73	3.34	0.73	3.36	0.73	A
19	store files in secondary storage devices	3.33	0.81	3.30	0.82	3.32	0.81	A
20	make use of computer assisted instruction to master certain course	2.89	0.75	2.87	0.76	2.88	0.75	A
21	handle minor problems in computer	2.89	0.70	2.86	0.70	2.87	0.70	A
22	use different computer application	3.04	0.80	2.96	0.79	2.99	0.80	A
23	rename files in computer system	3.05	0.79	3.02	0.77	3.03	0.77	A
24	use different computer application	2.93	0.65	2.91	0.60	2.92	0.62	A
25	copy files from hard disk to flash drive and versa	2.82	0.83	2.89	0.79	2.87	0.80	A
26	create sub directory/folder	2.89	0.75	2.97	0.69	2.94	0.71	A
27	rename sub directory/folder	2.89	0.79	2.92	0.79	2.91	0.79	A

28	open documents inside sub directory/folder	3.35	0.55	3.41	0.56	3.39	0.55	A
29	retrieve files for modification	3.00	0.88	3.04	0.85	3.03	0.86	A
30	adjust the default setting in an application	3.09	0.91	3.11	0.89	3.10	0.90	A
Cluster Mean/SD		3.09	0.75	3.09	0.74	3.10	0.74	A

The data presented in Table 3 indicates that overall item mean score ranges from 2.87 to 3.39 depicting agree. This shows that the items are the o computer operating competency needs of business educators in colleges of education for effective performance in Anambra State. The overall cluster mean rating of 3.10 indicates agree. This implies that the itemized

are the computer operating competency needs of business educators in colleges of education for effective performance in Anambra State. The low standard deviation of 0.74 shows that the respondent’s opinions do not differ remarkably to the itemized.

Hypothesis 2

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of mean ratings of male and female business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State with respect to Computer Operations Competency needs for effective performance

Variables	N	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	57	.012	147	.990	.01201	.99878	NS
Female	92						

The result of t-test analysis in Table 4 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significant and 147 degree of freedom for the items is 0.012 with a significant value of 0.990. As the significant value of 0.990 is more than the 0.05 level of significant the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean ratings of male and female business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State with respect to computer operations competency needs for effective performance.

Discussion

The findings of this study are discussed in line with the two ICT competencies covered as follows:

Networking Competency Needs of Business Educators in Colleges of Education for Effective Performance

The study found that networking competencies are highly needed by business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State for effective performance The finding is in consonance with Okeke (2015) and Mbah and Ezeilo (2019) who

averred business educators need to develop networking competency as well as software management skill in order to perform effectively in a digital society. This implies that the identified networking competencies are still very important for effective work performance especially among business educators.

The findings also show that there is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State on their needed networking competencies for effective performance. This means that both male and female business educators agree that they highly need networking competencies for effective duty performance in their colleges. The findings are in line with Okeke (2015) that application of ICT skills in teaching and learning is not gender sensitive.

Computer Operating Competency Needs of Business Educators in Colleges of Education for Effective Performance

Findings of the study revealed that computer

operation competencies are highly needed for effective performance by business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State. This finding agrees with Nnaji (2019) and Okeke (2015) who affirmed that computer operation competencies enable individuals to effectively carry out different activities using the computer hardware and software. This means that without adequate acquisition of computer operation competencies, business educators will not effectively deliver the contents of the programme to suitably equip their students for success in paid or self-employment. Furthermore,

Conclusion

The study determined the networking and computer operation competencies needed for effective performance by business educators in colleges of education in Anambra State. The findings revealed that these two ICT competencies are highly needed by business educators in the state for effective performance irrespective of gender. Based on these findings, the study concludes that business educators in the area of study and other parts of the country will hardly perform their functions effectively unless they are adequately equipped with relevant ICT competencies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Business educators should engage in in-service training programmes to develop networking and computer operation competencies for effective

REFERENCES

Ajegbelem, A. J. (2016). The Use of ICT to enhance university education in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education Learning and Development*, 4(5), 1 -11.

Aji-Safe, O.E, Bolariwa, K.O. & Edeh, T. (2015). Issues in Business education programs challenges to national transformation *Journal of education and practices* 6 (21): 208-212

the findings revealed that gender did not significantly influence the mean ratings of the respondents on the computer operation competencies they need for effective performance. This finding agrees with Okafor (2017) that all business educators, irrespective of gender, require computer and smart devices operation competencies for effective performance in instructional delivery. The similarity of the findings of the current and previous studies indicates how valuable computer operation competencies are in this dispensation of digitization and globalization.

curriculum implementation in colleges of education in Anambra State.

2. Management of colleges of education in Anambra State should support and sponsor business educators to in-service training programmes such as short courses, conferences, seminars and workshops on ICT skills acquisition for effective work performance.

3. Government and curriculum developers in Business Education should emphasize and adequately provide facilities to enable students develop relevant ICT competencies for effective work performance upon graduation.

4. The Association of Business Educators of Nigeria (ABEN) should organize and support their members to participate in conferences, seminars and workshops on ICT skills to enhance their effective work performance.

Digital Literacy (2017). Welcome to ALA's Literacy Clearinghouse. Retrieved from <https://literacy.ala.org/digital-literacy/>

Edokpolor, J. E. & Egbri, J. N. (2017). Business education in Nigeria for value re-orientation: a strategic approach for poverty alleviation and national development. *Journal of Educational Research and Review*. 5(3); 41-48.

- Eze T. A. (2016). Teacher's perception on the impact of training and retraining on teacher's productivity in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Quest Journals of Research in Business and Management*, 4(3) 33-37.
- Ezeabii, I. C. (2017). Entrepreneurial planning and organizational skills needed by business education students in public universities in South-East States of Nigeria for self-employment. *Nigeria Journal of Business Education* 4 (2) 195-204.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) Revised (2018). *National Policy on Education*. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Ismail, S. & Mohammed, D. S. (2015). Employability Skills in TVET curriculum in Nigeria Federal University of Technology. *Procedia Social and Behaviourial Science* 20 73-80
- Mbah, C. O. & Odike, F. I. (2021). Influence of ICT innovations in vocational education for achieving sustainable development in Anambra State. Conference paper presented at 3rd international multi-disciplinary conference of Faculty of Education Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University with the theme; education and innovations for sustainable development in Africa 16th to 19th of March, 2021.
- Nnaji, I.A (2019). Utilization of ICT in Teaching and Learning of Economics in Secondary Schools in Nsukka Education Zone. *International Journal of Economics Education Research*, 1(1), 43-57.
- Nwachukwu, V. N. (2017). Utilization of Computer Technology for Academic work by Lecturers of University of Jos-Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Sciences Studies*.1 (2), 14-22.
- Odokor, G. C. (2017). Application of mobile learning as a delivery technique in business education. *Journal of Technical Vocational Education Training and Research* 2(1) 120-133.
- Ofojebe, W.N. & Chukwuma, E.T.C. (2015). Utilization of continuous professional development of academic staff effectiveness in the higher education sector in contemporary Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Educational Research and Policy Studies* 6 (14) 306-314.
- Okafor, E.C. (2017). *ICT Employability Competencies possessed by Business Education graduates for sustainable economic empowerment in North-West zone of Nigeria*. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis. Department of Technology and Vocational Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology.
- Okeke F.P. (2015). *E-learning in Universities: Issues and challenges*. Retrieved on 3/7/2020 from http://www.e-learning/in_iversities/Nigerian_challenges.
- Okeke, A.F. (2017). *Influence of new technologies in teaching business education programme in Anambra State*. Unpublished B.Sc. Project Report. Department of Vocational Education Odumegwu Ojukwu University Awka.
- Okereke, G. K. O. & Obe, P. I. (2017). E-teaching competencies for capacity building of lecturers for effective delivery of technical education courses in universities in South-East. *Journal of Technical Vocational Education Training and Research* 2(1) 31-

328.

Okigbo, E. C. & Okeke, M.N. (2012). Challenges Facing Mathematics Teachers in the Utilization of ICT Elements for Mathematics Instruction, *International Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 4(1), 70-76.

Olaniyi, O. N. (2022). Digital skills and future of business education students. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Education Research* 4 (1) 186-192.

Oriji, A. & Anikpo, F. (2019). Social media in teaching-learning process; investigation of the use of Whatsapp in teaching and learning in university of Port-Harcourt. *European Scientific Journal* 15 (4) 15-39.

Rogers, E.M. (1962). A school direct develops management-based objectives (MOB) model. *Catalyst for change*, 12(2) 127-133.

Simens, G. (2004). Connectivism: learning theory for the digital age. *E-learn space*. Retrieved on 2/7/2018 from <http://www.elearnspace.org/articles/connectirism.htm>.

Super, D.E. (1957). Vocational adjustment; implementing a self-concept occupation. Retrieved on 22/23/2019 from <http://www.vocationaladjustment/self-concept/edu.com>.

Tanis, V. N. (2015). Historical Development of Cost and Management Accounting in Europe and US. Retrieved from [http://ilkerbulat.com/Icerik/File/Veyis%20N.%20Tanis%20\(YAY6\).pdf](http://ilkerbulat.com/Icerik/File/Veyis%20N.%20Tanis%20(YAY6).pdf)

Ugwu, J. C. (2013). ICT skills needed by business studies teachers in secondary schools in Awgu education Zones of Enugu State. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 3(21), 118-124.

Uzoagulu, A.E. (2013). *Practical Guide to Writing Research Report in Tertiary Institutions*. Enugu; John Jacobs Classic Publishers Ltd.

Wang, L. C. & Morgan, W. R. (2018). Students' perceptions of using instant messaging software to facilitate synchronous online class interaction in a graduate teacher education course. *Journal of Computing I Teacher Education* 25 (1), 15-21.